

FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION IN PREGNANT WOMEN IN THE BUKHARA REGION.

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Abstract. In the Bukhara Region, 40,818 pregnant women were placed on dispensary records in 2020, and 42,241 pregnant women in 2021. The medical histories of 120 pregnant women who were receiving treatment at the center established in the region for pregnant individuals infected with coronavirus infection were analyzed. During the pandemic, this center was established in the Bukhara Region to provide qualified medical assistance during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period.

Keywords: Covid, method, treatment, diagnosis, Bukhara.

According to the analysis results, 14% of pregnant women are in the age range of 18-20 years, 42% are in the age range of 20-30 years, and 44% are 30 years and older. Of the pregnant women, 23% reside in urban areas, while 77% reside in rural areas. Among them, 37% are experiencing their first pregnancy, 34% their second pregnancy, and 29% their third or subsequent pregnancies. Additionally, 11% are at 11-12 weeks of pregnancy, 17% are at 17-20 weeks, and 72% are beyond 20 weeks of pregnancy.

Among pregnant women, the course of coronavirus infection was observed in 6% of mild cases, 76% of moderate to severe cases, and 18% of severe cases. Of the 120 pregnant women, 14% were treated for up to 5 days, 45% for 5-10 days, and 41% for more than 10 days.

The clinical course of the disease among the 120 pregnant individuals infected with the coronavirus is as follows: cough - 87%, fever - 20%, loss of taste and smell - 37%, shortness of breath - 40%, sore throat - 23%.

The most frequent complications of coronavirus infection are unilateral pneumonia (right-sided or left-sided) - 23%, pneumonia with respiratory failure - 15%, and bronchitis - 5%.

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